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Malaria infection activates HLA-H for immune evasion.

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We measured total transcription in the blood in humans: in healthy individuals and in patients infected with Plasmodium: asymptomatic or symptomatic, to identify genes that define Malaria infection in vivo. We demonstrate here selective activation of the interferon stimulated gene Ifi27 in humans with Malaria infection, both symptomatic and asymptomatic infection. We describe induction of DNA damage during active infection with Malaria indicated by H2AX activation in both symptomatic and asymptomatic infection. Interestingly, we observed activation of class I MHC receptor HLA-H in the blood, during asymptomatic but not symptomatic infection. Malaria infection activates HLA-H for immune evasion.

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